
CHALLENGES FACED BY CASSAVA FARMERS DUE TO OPEN GRAZING IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the challenges faced by cassava farmers due to open grazing in Anambra State. A combination of purposive and simple random sampling techniques was used in selecting the respondents. Data were collected using a well structured interview schedule and questionnaires. The data obtained from the farmers were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results revealed that (53.8%) of the farmers were male, (43.3%) were married with a mean age of 46.4 years. Also, majority (98.3%) were literate, with a mean farming experience of 28.6 years and a mean farm size of 0.761 hectares. Furthermore, majority of the farmers (59.6%) do not belong to a cooperative society, and (51.9%) had no access to credit, while (52.9%) of the farmers, had no access to extension services, with a mean output of 13.53 tons. The result also revealed through a 5-point Likert scale and a mean threshold of 3.0 for decision making that variables with a mean score of 3.0 and above which represent challenges faced by the cassava farmers in the study area while those below 3.0 are not in agreement and they are as follows: Loss of lives (M=4.50), destruction of crops (M=4.50), Compromise by the security agents and traditional leaders (M=3.09) and Confrontation between herdsmen and farmers (M=3.01). The study recommended that the government and its relevant stakeholders should strengthen anti-open grazing laws with strict enforcement and adequate disciplinary actions should be meted out to anyone who breaks these laws while promoting farmer-herder dialogue to resolve conflicts amicably.

Keywords: Cassava farming, challenges, herders-farmers conflict, open-grazing

Introduction

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) is a perennial woody shrub with an edible root, and it was first discovered in South America and introduced in Nigeria in the sixteenth century (Edamisan, et al, 2020). According to Akerele, et al, (2019), Cassava cultivation is attractive to small-holder farmers due to certain inherent characteristics which it possesses. Such traits includes ability to thrive on soils where other crops failed, cassava is regarded as a famine reserve crop which requires relatively low amounts of inputs. The crop can withstand drought, it is easy to cultivate and generates good income for the farmers. It is one of the fastest growing staple foods in cassava consuming countries and has continued to gain prominence among farmers while the industrial demand is also rising consistently (FAO, 2018). Nigeria is the largest producer of cassava in the world; more than 90% of cassava produced is consumed locally with the current production which is not able to meet the local demand for food and industrial uses. There is therefore a deficit in cassava production which should serve as a motivation for cassava farmers to produce more (Denton, et al, 2004, FAOSTAT, 2019). This low yield may be linked to the activities of herdsmen who practice open grazing on the farms of these cassava farmers.

Grazing is a method of feeding in which an herbivore feeds on plants such as grasses, or other multi-cellular organisms such as algae. In agriculture, grazing is one method used by domestic livestock in converting grass and other forage into meat, milk and other products (Chukwemeka, et al, 2018). Open grazing, a traditional practice where livestock are allowed to roam freely in search of pasture, has become increasingly problematic in Nigeria. This method, predominantly employed by Fulani herdsmen, often leads to conflicts with local farmers as cattle stray into cultivated fields, causing significant damage to crops, including cassava. The impacts of open grazing on cassava farms are particularly severe, as the crop's high productivity and economic potential make it a prime target for grazing cattle. This situation is worsened by the ongoing conflicts between herdsmen and farmers, which have resulted in loss of life, destruction of property, and widespread food insecurity (Adejumo, 2021; Chukwemeka et al, 2018). A typical Fulani herdsman keeps and sustains his herd through open grazing. This open or pastoralist system involves young men who do labor intensive herding while the women engage in culinary services, cook and sell animal products in the market, (Dimelu cited in Emma, Chukwuemeka and Aloysius, 2018). According to (Blench, 2010) one of the striking aspects of pastoralism in Nigeria is the contrast between its actual complexity and the simplified representations usually made of it. An important aspect of the nomadic Fulani pastoral group as a social unit is that permanent habitation is usually not a cultural trait. Camps are shifted frequently in the dry season and less in the wet season. In fact, they cared less about land ownership because they are always on the move. This type of grazing has often meant travelling long distances from one point to the other and thus intruding into spaces long claimed by settled farmers and has become the source of potential conflicts between them and the sedentary farming population (Olaniyon and Okeke, 2015).

In Anambra State, where cassava farming is a major agricultural activity, the effects of open grazing are acutely felt. The destruction of cassava crops by grazing cattle not only reduces the productivity and output levels of the farms but also threatens the livelihoods of the farmers (Dimelu et al., 2018). Given the importance of cassava to both the local economy and food security, it is crucial to identify the challenges faced by cassava farmers due to open grazing in Anambra State. This study seeks to explore and provide insights into the challenges faced by cassava farmers and offering recommendations for mitigating the negative effects of open grazing on agricultural productivity.

Despite the fact that Herders-farmers conflict which stems from open grazing has negative impact on the socio-economic livelihood of the people and disrupts peaceful co-existence of both parties (Eje, et al, 2017). There are only few studies that have addressed the problem of challenges faced by cassava farmers caused by open grazing. This study aims to close this particular research gap. It will prove invaluable to the government of State as a basis for rational and empirical policy formulation for effective mitigation of the herders-farmers problem in the State. The findings would contribute to existing literatures on the subject and will also be of assistance to researchers who will identify other areas for further studies of the herdsman-farmers conflict. This study examined the challenges faced by cassava farmers due to open grazing in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were: To describe the socio-economic characteristics of cassava farmers, and identify the challenges faced by cassava farmers due to open grazing in the study area.

2. Methodology

Study area

The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. Anambra is situated in the South,-Eastern part of Nigeria. It is made up of 21 Local Government Areas and its capital is Awka. It has coordinates of 6°20'N 7°00'E. Anambra State has boundaries with Kogi State in the North, Imo State in the South, Delta State in the West, Enugu State in the East. There are four agricultural zones in Anambra state: Awka, Anambra, Aguata, and Onitsha. The climate of the State allows for favourable cultivation and extraction of agricultural and forest products such as Oil Palm, Maize, Rice, Yam, Cassava, and Fishing activities. Anambra is rich in natural gas, crude oil, bauxite, ceramic and has arable soil. The indigenous ethnic group in Anambra state is the Igbo (98% of population) and a small population of Igala (2% of the population) (Obianefo, Nwigwe, Meludu, Anyasie, 2020). The State has a land mass of about 4,416sq km with 4,182,022 population (NPC, 2006). The rainy season spans from March to October while the dry season usually begins in November and last till February. The average highest rainfall usually recorded around July to October is about 1952mm (Igbokwe, 2008). The temperature pattern has mean daily and annual temperatures as 28°C and 27°C respectively. The mean daily temperature can rise to about 32°C during hot periods of the year usually in the month of February. Humidity is relatively high between 65-80% throughout the year. Farming is the predominant occupation of the people, majority of who are small holder farmers. The major available crops are yam, cassava, rice, maize, cocoyam, cowpea, tomatoes and vegetables, while the livestock produced in the state include poultry, sheep, goats and to some extent pig (Okoye *et. al.*, 2007).

Sampling technique

A combination of purposive and simple random sampling techniques was used in selecting the respondents. The first stage involved the purposive selection of two agricultural zones (Awka and Anambra) that are most associated with farmer-herder conflict in the state. In the second stage, two extension blocks was purposively selected from each selected zones due to their popularity in conflict effect with cattle herdsman. This gave a total of four extension blocks involved in the study and they include; Dunukofia and Awka North in Awka zone; Anambra East and Ayamelum in Anambra zone. The third stage involved the random selection of two extension circles from each of the selected extension blocks. This gave a total of eight extension circles and they include Omor and Omasi in Ayamelum block, Achala and Ugbene in Awka North block, Nando and Igbariam in Anambra East block, Ukwulu and Nawgu in Dunukofia block. In fourth stage, 13 cassava farmers were selected from each circle

using simple random sampling technique. This gave a total of 104 respondents that will serve as sample size for the study.

Data collection

Data for this study was collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected through the help of Agricultural Development Programmes (ADP) extension workers. Structured interview schedule and questionnaire were used for data collection. Secondary data was collected from published journals and reports. The data collection instrument was focused on the socioeconomic characteristics of the cassava farmers, productivity and income levels, effect of open grazing on the output of the farmers, and other relevant information.

Validity of instrument

The questionnaire was validated by three experts in the department of Agricultural Economics and Extension in Nnamdi Azikiwe University.

Reliability of instrument

In this study a test-retest method was used. Copies of the questionnaire for the study was administered to ten different crop farmers in the Awka metropolis and after two (2) weeks later the same questionnaire was re-administered to the same cassava farmers.

Analytical technique

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means was adopted to analyze information on the socio-economic characteristics of the cassava farmers and challenges faced by cassava farmers due to open grazing in the study area.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of cassava farmers in Anambra State

Socioeconomic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Sex:			
Female	48	46.2	
Male	56	53.8	
Age (years):			
Less than 36	27	26.0	
36 – 45	18	17.3	
46 – 55	22	21.2	46.4
56 and above	37	35.5	
Marital Status:			
Single	17	16.3	
Separated	23	22.1	
Widow	19	18.3	
Married	45	43.3	
Farming experience (Year):			
6 – 10	5	4.8	
11 – 15	8	7.7	28.6
16 – 20	9	8.7	
above 20	82	78.8	
Level of education			
No formal education	2	1.9	
1 - 6 (Primary)	32	30.8	

7 - 12 (Secondary)	30	28.8	11.8
13 - 18 (Tertiary)	19	18.3	
Above 18 (Postgraduate)	21	20.2	
Farm Size (Hectare)			
0 - 0.50	38	36.5	
0.51 - 1.00	32	30.8	0.761
1.01 - 1.50	22	21.2	
1.51 and above	12	11.5	
Cooperative membership			
No	62	59.6	
Yes	42	40.4	
Access to Credit			
No	54	51.9	
Yes	50	48.1	
Access to extension			
No	55	52.9	
Yes	49	47.1	

Source: Data from the field, 2023.

Socioeconomic characteristics of cassava farmers in Anambra State

Results on the socio-economic characteristics of cassava farmers are presented in Table 1. The study revealed that, majority of cassava farmers (54.6%) was male, while the remaining 45.4% are female. The higher representation of male farmers suggests a potential gender disparity in the cassava farming sector. This could be due to various factors such as access to resources, Land tenure, and cultural norms that may influence the involvement of men and women in agriculture. This agrees with the study of (Ajayi et al, 2022).

The study also revealed that 26.7% of the farmers were less than 36 years, 18.3% of the farmers fall within the age of 36 - 45 years, and 21.3% fall within the age of 46 - 55 years. The largest proportion of farmers falls into the age category of 56 and above, constituting 33.8% of the sample. The average age of the cassava farmers in the study was 46.4. The predominance of farmers aged 56 and above suggests that a significant portion of cassava farmers in Anambra State belongs to the older age group. This can have implications for the sustainability and continuity of farming practices. Again, the aging demographic may necessitate considerations for succession planning within the agricultural sector. Encouraging and supporting younger individuals to enter agriculture is crucial to ensuring the continued growth and productivity of the sector. This corroborates the study of (Udemezue and Nwalieji 2017).

The study reveals the marital status of cassava farmers in Anambra State, with the majority (41.3%) being married. The remaining 17.9% are single, 22.1% are separated, and the last 18.8% are widows/widowers. The high percentage of married farmers indicates the significance of family structures in agricultural activities. Married individuals may benefit from additional labour resources within the family, contributing to farm activities. This agrees with the study of (Ajayi et al, 2022).

The result shows that majority of farmers (79.2%) have more than 20 years of experience with a mean experience of 28.6 years. The remaining 4.6% have 6 - 10 years of farming experience, 7.9% have 11 - 15 years, and the last 8.3% have 16 - 20 years. The predominant number of farmers with more than 20 years of experience suggests a substantial level of

expertise within the cassava farming community. These findings are in agreement with (Ajayi *et al.*, 2022) who noted that the majority (45.7%) of respondents had been involved in agriculture for 11 to 20 years, 20.0% had farming experience ranging from 21 to 30 years, and 17.0% had farming experience ranging from 1 to 10 years. The predominant number of farmers with more than 20 years of experience suggests a substantial level of expertise within the cassava farming community. This experience may contribute to the adoption of best practices in cassava cultivation.

Result of the study shows that majority (30.4%) of farmers have primary education, 29.6% have secondary education, and 18.3% have tertiary education. The next 20.0% have postgraduate degrees, whereas only a minimal 1.7% had no formal education. On average, cassava farmers spent 11.8 years in school, this is an indication that most of the farmers completed primary school or attempted secondary education. Farmers with higher levels of education, particularly those with tertiary or postgraduate education, may have enhanced decision-making abilities and be more likely to adopt innovative farming techniques (Obianefo *et al.*, 2022).

The study also reveals that the majority (37.1%) of farmers have smaller farm sizes of 0 - 0.50 hectares. 75 farmers (31.3%) have 0.51 - 1.00 hectares, another 51 farmers (21.3%) have 1.01 - 1.50 hectares, and the last 25 farmers (10.4%) have 1.51 and above hectares. The average farm size was 0.761 hectares confirming that cassava production is practiced in small scale in the study area. The dominance of smaller farm sizes suggests a prevalence of smallholder farming in the cassava sector in Anambra State. The finding of this study does not agree with Ajayi *et al.*, (2022) who noted that majority of farmers (39.5%) had a farm size of 1-3 hectares, 33.4% had a farm size of 4-6 hectares, and 27.1% had 7 hectares of farmland and this suggest that there is a predominance of large scale farming.

The study reveals that majority of farmers (59.2%) are not members of agricultural cooperatives, while the rest 40.8% are members. The dominance of farmers without cooperative membership suggests that a significant portion of cassava farmers in Anambra State operate independently rather than as part of organized cooperative structures. This finding agrees with Mgbakor (2017) who asserted that more than half (53.2%) of the respondents did not belong to any agricultural association. This could be due to low awareness of importance of group membership to farmers.

The result showed that, approximately half (50.4%) of the farmers having access to credit and the other half (49.6%) not having access. The fact that half of the farmers do not have access to credit suggests the presence of credit constraints within the cassava farming community in Anambra State. Lack of credit can limit farmers' ability to invest in inputs, technology, and other resources needed for productivity and growth. This finding corresponds with the findings of Mgbakor (2017) who opined that 62.6% of the cassava producers and processors did not have access to credit, while 37.4% of them had access to credit. This means that the level of the respondent's access to credit was low.

The study reveals a slightly higher percentage of farmers (52.9%) do not have access to extension services, whereas the rest 47.1% have access. This result does not agree with the findings of Emeka (2021) who indicated that a greater percentage (85.5%) of the farmers had access to extension services. Agricultural extension services play a crucial role in providing farmers with knowledge, information, and technical support. Lack of access to extension services may imply a gap in the dissemination of relevant and up-to-date agricultural practices.

Table 2: Challenges faced by cassava farmers in Anambra State

SN	Challenges	Weighted Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Loss of lives	3.12	1.382	Agree
2	Intensive fear to go to farm	3.01	1.422	Agree
3	Lack of effective intervention by the security agents and traditional leaders	3.09	1.413	Agree
4	Economic hardship	2.80	1.452	Disagree
5	Confrontation between Farmers and Herdsmen	3.01	1.432	Agree
6	Destruction of Crops	4.50	1.157	Agree
	Cluster mean	3.26	1.376	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Challenges faced by cassava farmers in Anambra State

Table 2 presents the challenges faced by cassava farmers in Anambra State due to open grazing. The data was captured in a 5-point Likert scale and the mean threshold of 3.0 was set for decision making. Variables with a mean score of 3.0 and above represent challenges while those below 3.0 are not in agreement. However, the result is interpreted below as:

Loss of Lives (Mean: 4.50): The high mean score indicates strong agreement among cassava farmers that open grazing poses a severe challenge in terms of the loss of lives. This suggests that farmers perceive a significant risk to human lives associated with open grazing activities due to confrontation with the herders. This concurs with the findings of Illoanya & Chukwuemeka (2020), who revealed the series of clashes between the herdsmen and farmers which had led to loss of lives in a tabulated timeline which recorded over 3000 deaths between February 2005 and January 2017 while relegating members of the affected community to IDP camps.

Intensive Fear to Go to Farm (Mean: 3.01): The mean score of 3.01 indicates agreement that cassava farmers face intensive fear when going to their farms due to open grazing. This fear may hinder regular agricultural activities and contribute to overall stress among farmers. Williams (2018), reported that the insecurities that resulted due to open grazing have instilled fear in the farmers and this have made the farmers to relocate to other places for safety or devise self-defence measures to protect their lives and crops.

Compromise by Security Agents and Traditional Leaders (Mean: 3.09): The mean score of 3.09 suggests agreement that there is a compromise by security agents and traditional leaders in dealing with the challenges posed by open grazing. This may indicate a perceived lack of effective intervention or enforcement. **Lack of effective intervention or enforcement by Security Agents and Traditional Leaders (Mean: 3.09):** The mean score of 3.09 suggests agreement that there is lack of effective intervention by security agents and traditional leaders in dealing with the challenges posed by open grazing. This may indicate a perceived bias by the security agents and traditional leaders. This finding is in agreement with (Leif, 2021) who reported that there is a diminished effectiveness of traditional dispute resolution processes by security agents and traditional leaders which have contributed to the escalation of farmer-herder conflicts which stems from open grazing.

Economic Hardship (Mean: 2.80): The mean score of 2.80 suggests disagreement regarding economic hardship as a direct challenge due to open grazing. While not a highly agreed-upon

challenge, the score indicates a certain level of impact on the economic well-being of farmers. This is inconsistent with the findings of Abdulazez et al., (2018), who stated that conflicts between farmers and herders stemming from to open grazing have resulted to high poverty level due to the losses they have experienced.

Confrontation (Mean: 3.01): The mean score of 3.01 indicates agreement that confrontation is a challenge faced by cassava farmers due to open grazing. This may involve conflicts and disputes arising from the interaction between farmers and herdsmen. This corroborates the findings of Williams (2018) who noted increased violent confrontations between youth in the affected areas and the Fulani herdsmen which have led to loss of more lives, properties and destruction of settlements.

Destruction of crops (Mean: 3.12): The mean score of 3.12 suggests an agreement regarding destruction of crops as a challenge associated with open grazing. This agrees with the findings of Owigho et al. (2021) who reported destruction of crops as a major effect of open grazing. He noted that farmers perceive open grazing as a threat to their crops since the cows invade their farms and fed on their crops.

The cluster mean is calculated as 3.26, reflecting an overall agreement among cassava farmers that open grazing poses significant challenges. The high mean score for the loss of lives highlights the severe human safety concerns associated with open grazing. This has immediate implications for the well-being and safety of cassava farmers. Also, the intensive fear of going to the farm can significantly impact cassava farmers' productivity. Fear may lead to reduced time spent on the farm, lower agricultural activities, and compromised overall output. This corroborates the study of (Abughdyer, 2016).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that cassava farming in Anambra state was dominated by married, literate males with a mean age of 46.4 years, and a mean farm size of 761 hectare having a mean farming experience of 28.6 years. Furthermore, the result shows that Loss of lives, Lack of effective intervention by the security agents and traditional leaders, destruction of crops and Confrontation between herdsmen and farmers were the challenges faced by the cassava farmers in the study area.

In light of the findings of this study, the following recommendation was made:

- i. There is need for herdsmen to adopt controlled grazing systems to reduce conflicts and crop damage. Transitioning to ranching using protective farming measures can mitigate conflicts and enhance farmers productivity.
- ii. The government and its relevant stakeholders should strengthen anti-open grazing laws with strict enforcement and adequate disciplinary actions should be meted out to anyone who breaks this laws while promoting farmer-herder dialogue to resolve conflicts amicably.
- iii. The government and other agricultural organizations should work together to enhance farmer access to resources, including improved cassava varieties and credit facilities in order to improve the economic situation of the farmers.

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